

From medication to movement: The role of physical activity in the treatment of obesity

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Abstract

Background. Defined by a BMI ≥ 30 , obesity reflects excessive fat deposition linked to increased morbidity. Between 1990 and 2022, global obesity prevalence rose markedly: from 2% to 8% in youth and from 7% to 16% in adults (WHO). Therefore, the implementation of anti-obesity medications, physical exercise, and lifestyle interventions is of growing importance.

Aim. The objective of this article is to assess the role of physical activity in obesity therapy and to compare its efficacy and drawbacks with those of medical treatments.

Material and methods. In May 2025, we performed a search in the open-access PubMed database using the search terms: “(side effects) AND (anti-obesity medication)”. This search covered publications from the years 2020 to 2025 and initially returned 31 relevant studies. Additional relevant studies were identified through reference lists and a supplementary PubMed search, allowing inclusion of some pre-2020 literature. In total, 52 articles were included.

Results. The study explores multiple anti-obesity strategies, including medications such as Liraglutide, Semaglutide, Tirzepatide, Exenatide, Orforglipron, Retatrutide, Vutiglabin, and Orlistat, as well as natural compounds and other investigational drugs. The paper also considers physical activity as an integral aspect of obesity management, examining its therapeutic potential and integration with drug-based treatments.

Conclusions. Complementing pharmacological treatment with physical activity is essential for effective obesity management and is vital for sustaining weight loss once pharmacological interventions have ended.

Key words: obesity, physical activity, anti-obesity drugs

1. Introduction

Obesity is defined as excessive fat accumulation that poses a significant risk to health. A body mass index (BMI) of 30 or higher is classified as obese. In 2019, an estimated 5 million deaths from noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) were attributed to obesity-related health risks associated with a higher-than-optimal BMI [1]. Obesity increases the risk of developing numerous complications, including type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease and some cancers [2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. The global prevalence of obesity continues to rise among both adults and children. According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO), between 1990 and 2022, the percentage of children and adolescents aged 5-19 years living with obesity increased four-fold, from 2% to 8%. Among adults aged 18 years and older, the rate of obesity more than doubled, growing from 7% to 16% over the same period [1].

Currently, obesity is recognized as one of the five leading causes of death worldwide. The risk of mortality increases significantly with body weight by 20-40% in individuals who are overweight, and by as much as 200-400% in those who are obese. It is estimated that excessive body weight including both overweight and obesity is responsible for approximately 3.4 million deaths annually [7].

However, contemporary research indicates the key importance of physical activity not only as a tool supporting weight loss, but also as an independent therapeutic factor influencing metabolism, body composition, insulin sensitivity and the patient's mental health [2, 3, 4].

The aim of this article is to review the current scientific evidence on the role of physical activity in the treatment of obesity and to compare its effectiveness and limitations in relation to pharmacological treatment.

2. Research materials and methods

In May 2025, we performed a search in the open-access PubMed database using the search terms: “(side effects) AND (anti-obesity medication)”. As an initial inclusion criterion, we considered studies classified as clinical trials or randomized clinical trials. This search covered publications from the years 2020 to 2025 and initially returned 31 relevant studies. Additional relevant publications were found by examining the reference lists of the included articles and a supplementary search PubMed, enabling us to add some pre-2020 literature. We included articles in English classified as original research, observational studies, systematic reviews, case reports or literature reviews. Ultimately, 52 articles were included. The manuscript was subsequently reviewed and edited by all authors to guarantee uniformity and accuracy.

3. Research results

Overview of Anti-Obesity Drugs, Their Side Effects, and Withdrawal Effects

3.1. Semaglutide

Semaglutide, a GLP-1 analogue, has been extensively studied in numerous clinical trials. The STEP-1 study showed that semaglutide 2.4 mg once weekly, as an adjunct to lifestyle modification, led to clinically significant weight loss in overweight or obese patients. Similarly, the STEP-2 study confirmed the superior efficacy of semaglutide 2.4 mg once weekly compared to 1.0 mg and placebo, both in the treatment of obesity and in patients with type 2 diabetes [5, 8, 9, 10].

The STEP-3 study evaluated the efficacy of semaglutide as an adjunct to intensive behavioral therapy in overweight or obese individuals. The results showed that semaglutide led to significantly greater weight loss over 68 weeks compared to placebo [5, 9, 11]. The STEP-4 study focused on the maintenance of weight loss over time, showing that semaglutide promotes further, sustained weight loss [5, 10]. In contrast, the STEP-5 study examined the long-term effects of semaglutide treatment in overweight or obese adults over a two-year period. It found that semaglutide treatment led to significant and sustained weight loss [5, 9].

The STEP-6 study evaluated the efficacy of semaglutide in obese East Asian adults with and without type 2 diabetes. It found that semaglutide at a dose of 2.4 mg once weekly led to significantly greater weight loss and reductions in abdominal visceral fat volume compared with placebo. These results suggest that semaglutide is a promising treatment option for weight management in this population [5, 12].

The STEP 7 study was a randomized, multicenter, double-blind, controlled phase 3a study conducted at 23 clinical sites in China, Hong Kong, Brazil, and South Korea. Participants were overweight or obese adults with or without type 2 diabetes. They were randomly assigned 2:1 to receive semaglutide 2.4 mg once weekly or placebo for 44 weeks, with concurrent diet and exercise intervention. Randomization was performed in a block design (6-person block) using an interactive web-based response system, stratified by type 2 diabetes. Participants, investigators, and sponsors were blinded to treatment allocation until database cut-off. Primary endpoints were percent change in body weight and the percentage of participants who achieved at least a 5% weight loss from baseline at week 44. All participants who received at least one dose of study drug were included in the safety assessment. Of the 448 screened, 375 were randomized to semaglutide (n=249) or placebo (n=126). The mean estimated change in body weight was -12.1% (SE 0.5) in the semaglutide group versus -3.6% (SE 0.7) in the placebo group, corresponding to a difference of -8.5 percentage points (95% CI: -10.2 to -6.8; $p < 0.0001$). Weight loss of $\geq 5\%$ was achieved by 85% of participants in the semaglutide group (203/238) compared with 31% in the placebo group (36/116), with an odds ratio of 13.1 (95% CI: 7.4–23.1; $p < 0.0001$). Adverse events were reported in 93% of participants in the semaglutide group and 86% in the placebo group, with gastrointestinal events being the most common (67% vs 36%, respectively) [13].

In the STEP-8 study, the efficacy of once-weekly semaglutide was compared with daily liraglutide. The mean weight loss was -15.8% for semaglutide and -6.4% for liraglutide (difference: -9.4 pp; 95% CI: -12.0 to -6.8; $p < 0.001$), compared with -1.9% in the placebo group. A significantly greater proportion of participants receiving semaglutide achieved weight loss of $\geq 10\%$ (70.9% vs 25.6%), $\geq 15\%$ (55.6% vs 12.0%), and $\geq 20\%$ (38.5% vs 6.0%) compared with liraglutide, all differences being statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). These results confirm the superior efficacy of semaglutide in reducing body weight and improving cardiometabolic risk factors, making it a promising option in the treatment of obesity and its complications [5].

The STEP-TEENS study provides important data on the treatment of obesity in adolescents. Semaglutide resulted in a mean reduction in BMI of 16.1% over 68 weeks compared with placebo (difference: -16.7 pp; 95% CI: -20.3 to -13.2; $p < 0.001$). At least a 5% reduction in body weight was achieved by 73% of participants taking semaglutide, compared with 18% in the placebo group (OR: 14.0; 95% CI: 6.3–31.0; $p < 0.001$). The drug also showed beneficial effects on waist circumference, HbA1c, lipids (except HDL), and ALT levels. Although the results are promising, further studies are needed to assess the long-term safety and efficacy of the therapy [5, 14].

3.2. Liraglutide

Liraglutide is a synthetic equivalent of human glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), a hormone that affects insulin and glucagon secretion in a manner dependent on blood glucose levels. Additionally, it plays an important role in regulating appetite, satiety, and energy intake. Initially, this drug was approved for the treatment of type 2 diabetes at doses of 1.2 mg or 1.8 mg per day, administered subcutaneously. Over time, at an increased dose of 3.0 mg per day, it also gained approval as a weight loss aid in combination with appropriate diet and physical activity [4, 5].

Initially approved for the treatment of type 2 diabetes, liraglutide has been shown to be effective in reducing body weight in obese people, both with and without diabetes. Studies have shown that the use of liraglutide at a dose of 3.0 mg per day, in combination with diet and exercise, leads to significant weight loss and improved glycemic control. Compared to other drugs such as orlistat, liraglutide has greater benefits in terms of weight loss and improvement of metabolic parameters. The most common adverse effects are gastrointestinal symptoms, mainly nausea, characteristic of GLP-1 receptor agonists. Despite its efficacy and good tolerability, further studies are needed on the safety and optimization of liraglutide dosing in the long term [4, 5].

A study by Lundgren et al. showed that combining liraglutide (3.0 mg/day) with aerobic exercise for 1 year in obese adults led to greater weight loss, fat reduction, and improvement of insulin sensitivity and cardiorespiratory fitness than using either component alone. Furthermore, no adverse effects of liraglutide treatment, such as increased heart rate or gallstone formation, were observed in the combined group [4].

Similar benefits have been reported in obese adolescents, where liraglutide combined with lifestyle changes resulted in significant weight loss. Animal studies have shown that the combination of liraglutide and physical activity lowers blood glucose and increases insulin, and also activates

brown adipose tissue and the browning of white tissue, which is crucial for thermogenesis and energy metabolism [4].

3.3. Exenatide

Exenatide is a glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor agonist used in the treatment of type 2 diabetes and obesity, which improves blood glucose control and promotes weight loss. Exenatide was initially approved for the treatment of type 2 diabetes and obesity in adults. Its safety and efficacy in children were subsequently evaluated in a pilot study and a three-month randomized controlled trial (RCT) [15, 16, 17, 18]. Weghuber et al. conducted a 6-month, parallel-group, double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial involving children and adolescents aged 10 to 18 years. The study took place at two clinical sites and compared the effects of once-weekly subcutaneous injections of exenatide 2 mg versus placebo, both in combination with a lifestyle intervention [15]. Their findings reveal for the first time that using long-acting exenatide in obese adolescents improves glycemic control and decreases levels of total and LDL cholesterol, alongside a moderate reduction in BMI. In adults with type 2 diabetes, both the twice-daily and once-weekly formulations of exenatide have previously been shown to reduce BMI. The reduction in BMI seen here is on par with that achieved through medications like orlistat or metformin [15, 19, 20]. As far as adverse events (AEs) are concerned, the number of AEs was similar between the treatment group and the placebo group. The most commonly reported adverse events were related to the gastrointestinal system – including flatulence, nausea, diarrhea, vomiting, and abdominal pain; infections of the respiratory, urinary, and gastrointestinal tracts; as well as headaches, syncope, and paresthesia. Gastrointestinal adverse events occurred more frequently in the exenatide group, while the incidence of infection-related and central nervous system-related adverse events was comparable between the exenatide and placebo groups [15]. Weghuber et al.'s study offers initial proof that using extended-release exenatide in adolescents with obesity is practical and results in a slight but measurable decrease in BMI. The findings highlight GLP-1 receptor agonists as a promising treatment option for this population, especially considering the limited availability of effective pharmacological therapies [15, 20].

3.4. Orforglipron

Orforglipron is an oral GLP-1 receptor agonist taken once daily. It's being developed to help manage weight and treat type 2 diabetes. Orforglipron is a partial receptor agonist that exhibited a greater influence on cAMP (cyclic AMP) signaling than on β -arrestin engagement, potentially resulting in reduced receptor desensitization compared to full receptor agonists. Wharton et al conducted double-blind, randomized study including adults who were either obese or overweight with associated health conditions, excluding those with diabetes. Subjects were randomly allocated to receive once daily one of four doses of orforglipron (12 mg, 24 mg, 36 mg, 45 mg) or a placebo over 36 weeks. Out of all enrolled 86% participants (235 patients) completed the trial, and 76% (207 patients) finished the treatment as assigned. Participants taking orforglipron experienced significant weight loss of up to 14.7% by week 36. Additionally, it improved cardiometabolic markers, including systolic blood pressure and lipid levels. Gastrointestinal side effects, including nausea (37% to 58% of participants) and vomiting (14% to 32% of participants), were the most common adverse effects, more frequent than with placebo. These events were generally low to moderate and resolved on their own. Severe adverse events were noted in seven patients receiving orforglipron, though the overall occurrence was similar to that seen with placebo. The liver function remained unchanged in both groups, and discontinuation due to side effects occurred in 10-17% participants, primarily related to gastrointestinal issues [21].

3.5. Tirzepatide

Tirzepatid is a molecule combining insulinotropic polypeptide with glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonism. This combination provides the possibility of joint cooperation affecting excessive appetite, food intake and body metabolism. It is used in the form of weekly subcutaneous injections in the treatment of type 2 diabetes and obesity [10, 22]. The SURMOUNT-4 study was conducted to assess the efficacy and safety of Tirzepatide in the long-term treatment of obesity. In the first phase of the study, each participant received the drug. The result of using Tirzepatide was a 20.9% weight loss. In the next stage of the study, people with stable body weight were divided into two groups. A group that continued to receive the drug and a placebo group. This phase lasted 52 weeks. The study showed that patients who continued treatment with the maximum tolerated dose of the drug for another 52 weeks maintained better weight loss effects and even further reduction. On the other hand, switching to placebo caused partial recovery of previous weight loss,

with an average body weight increase of 14%. The results of the study indicate that in order to maintain the effects of weight loss, the drug should be used long-term, which may be associated with the occurrence of side effects. The main side effects reported by patients included diarrhea, constipation, vomiting [22]. The SURMOUNT-1 to -4 studies confirm the occurrence of adverse effects related to gastrointestinal disorders. Their frequency increased with increasing the dose of the drug [10]. Tirzepatid is an effective drug in reducing body weight. Unfortunately, its effectiveness is maintained only with its chronic use, and the effects of the drug reverse very quickly after discontinuation of treatment [22].

3.6. Retatrutide

Retatrutide is a peptide conjugated with a fatty acid residue. It acts as an agonist for the glucagon (GCG), glucose-dependent insulintropic peptide (GIP) and glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1) receptors. It has the highest potency for the GIP receptor. The published phase II study examined the safety and efficacy of Retatrutide. The study involved adult patients with obesity who did not have type 2 diabetes. Retatrutide demonstrated good efficacy in reducing body weight. The subjects who received the highest dose of the drug lost an average of 24.2% of their body weight over 48 weeks of treatment. The placebo group lost only 2.1% of their body weight over the same period. However, the subjects receiving the drug experienced adverse effects from the gastrointestinal tract, including diarrhea, constipation, nausea and vomiting. The study did not examine the effects of discontinuing the drug. Due to the mechanism of action of the drug, there is a risk that after discontinuation of the drug, patients treated with Retatrutide may gradually regain the lost body weight. Therefore, further research in this direction is needed to assess the consequences of discontinuing long-term treatment [23].

3.7. Vutiglabin

Vutiglabin belongs to the group of synthetic derivatives of glabridin, which is obtained from licorice root. In preclinical studies, vutiglabin caused increased energy expenditure and reduced body weight, which is supposed to counteract obesity. Currently, Vutiglabin is undergoing clinical trials for the treatment of obesity in adults [24]. These studies focus on the safety of use and bioavailability of the drug. A randomized study was conducted, consisting of both single and multiple doses of the drug in healthy volunteers. Vutiglabin was well tolerated. Participants in

the study reported adverse effects mainly related to the gastrointestinal system, such as nausea and dyspepsia. There were no serious adverse effects that would require discontinuation of the drug [25]. The bioavailability study showed that the diet used has an effect on the absorption of the drug. Bioavailability increased after consuming a meal containing a large amount of fat [24, 25]. Pharmacodynamic analysis has shown that the drug has a beneficial effect on improving metabolism. Unfortunately, the study did not include observation after the end of the treatment. There is no information on the potential effects of discontinuing the drug. Further studies are needed to learn about the effects and consequences of long-term treatment and then its discontinuation. Vutiglavidin shows promising results as a drug in the treatment of obesity, but there are no studies on the safety profile of chronic therapy and its discontinuation in patients with obesity [25].

3.8. Orlistat

Orlistat is a lipase inhibitor. It inhibits the secretion of gastric and pancreatic lipase, thanks to which about 30% of fat from consumed food is not absorbed into the body. In a review of the clinical effectiveness of Orlistat therapy, the patients studied reduced their body weight by 3.1% more during one year of treatment than the participants who received a placebo instead of the drug. The higher the dose of the drug used, the greater the weight loss. Additionally, the drug had a positive effect on improving metabolism, cholesterol levels and glycemia control. Patients with type 2 diabetes and dyslipidemia also benefited. Long-term studies confirmed that the use of Orlistat for 4 years caused a significant reduction in body weight and reduced the risk of developing diabetes by 37% in people with its improper tolerance. Unfortunately, this drug causes side effects. Patients complain of abdominal discomfort, fat present in the stool, flatulence, steatorrhea and fecal incontinence. There have been cases of liver toxicity and incidents of pancreatitis. Due to the high number of side effects with a small weight loss, this drug is no longer used as often. Studies have also been conducted on Orlistat in the form of a mouthwash. The results of the study showed that rinsing with a mouthwash reduces the intake of calories from fat in people eating fatty meals. It was found that the administration of Orlistat in this form may affect the changed perception of the taste of fat in the mouth, which will cause less frequent reaching for fatty foods. However, the mouthwash had no positive effect on the subjects who did not follow a diet high in fat. The use of Orlistat in the form of a mouthwash may reduce the number of side

effects. However, there are currently no studies assessing the long-term effects of the drug and the effects of its discontinuation [26]. The study by Owen and Svacina (2006) examined the effect of discontinuing Orlistat treatment. It was shown that discontinuing treatment did not negatively affect body weight and glycemia levels, while no further benefits from treatment were observed in the following year [27]. The study by Grudén et al. (2021) assessed the safety of a new combination of substances in the treatment of obesity. The mutual synergistic effect of Orlistat with Acarbose was assessed. The results showed that the combination of Orlistat with Acarbose can be an effective strategy in the treatment of obesity. During therapy, the most frequently reported side effects were gastrointestinal symptoms such as bloating, diarrhea and excessive gas. However, as in the above-mentioned groups of drugs, there is a lack of studies on long-term therapy and the effect on discontinuation of therapy [28].

3.9. Plant-based natural compounds

In addition to synthetic drugs, plant-based natural compounds are gaining increasing attention for their effectiveness and safety in the treatment of obesity. *Gymnema sylvestre* (GS) and berberine (BBR) are plant-derived compounds that have shown promising therapeutic effects in managing obesity and its related conditions, offering a safe and effective alternative to conventional synthetic medications. Bandala C. et al. conducted a comparative study on patients with obesity treated with GS or BBR for a duration of three months. *Gymnema sylvestre*, a plant indigenous to central and southern India, has shown supportive effects in the management of type 2 diabetes by enhancing glucose control and boosting insulin responsiveness. Moreover, its supplementation may contribute to a healthier metabolic profile by positively affecting cholesterol levels and blood pressure [29, 30, 31, 32]. BBR, an alkaloid sourced from traditional Chinese plants like *Rhizoma coptidis*, *Cortex phellodendri*, and *Hydrastis canadensis*, has been found to support insulin function and boost glucose absorption by triggering the AMPK and TLR4 pathways. This positions it as a promising candidate for addressing metabolic syndrome and cardiovascular complications linked to obesity [29, 33, 34]. In the study conducted by Bandala C. et al., three months of treatment with GS resulted in reduced fasting glucose levels and body fat percentage, along with increased insulin levels compared to baseline. Meanwhile, patients receiving BBR showed reductions in body weight, BMI, and both total and visceral fat percentage relative to their initial measurements [29]. Han H.-S. et al. conducted a study aimed at evaluating the effects of *Hydrangea serrata* leaf extract

(WHS) on body weight and fat reduction in overweight or obese individuals. Hydrangea leaf extract is classified as GRAS (Generally Recognized as Safe), meaning it is considered safe for consumption in food and beverages. It is commonly enjoyed as an herbal tea. That study showed that taking 600 mg of WHS daily for 12 weeks led to significant decreases in body weight and fat mass, along with reductions in BMI, body fat percentage, hip measurements, visceral fat area, total abdominal fat area, and the ratio of visceral to subcutaneous fat. In summary, WHS shows potential as an effective supplement for combating obesity [35]. Laouani A. et al. conducted a study to evaluate the effectiveness of *Nitraria retusa* extract (NRE) in lowering body weight, BMI, body fat percentage, and various anthropometric measurements in overweight and obese women, with outcomes compared to a placebo group. This study is the first to show that taking 2000 mg/day of NRE for 12 weeks can lead to reductions in body weight, waist circumference, and BMI, primarily due to a loss of body fat accompanied by gains in body water and muscle mass. These results support NRE as a natural alternative to synthetic anti-obesity drugs [36].

3.10. Another Anti-obesity Agents

S-309309 is a new oral MGAT2 inhibitor being developed to treat obesity. The primary objective of first-in-human phase I trial by Ishibashi T. et al. was to evaluate the safety, tolerability, and pharmacokinetic profile of S-309309 after administering both single-escalating doses and multiple doses in healthy individuals, regardless of obesity status. Preclinical research indicates that it could serve as a treatment option for obesity and weight management, mainly by decreasing food consumption and boosting energy expenditure [37, 38]. Ishibashi T. et al. observed that the pharmacokinetics of S-309309 were similar in healthy adults regardless of obesity status. Therefore, administering multiple doses of up to 50 mg once daily is considered safe for obese patients in the upcoming phase II trial. S-309309 demonstrated effectiveness in managing body weight in a diet-induced obesity mouse model. Consequently, they are advancing S-309309 as a promising anti-obesity drug candidate with a unique mechanism of action. Their study demonstrated that S-309309 has a good safety profile and favorable pharmacokinetics, emphasizing its potential to fulfill unmet needs in obesity treatment [37]. Intranasal oxytocin has emerged as a promising therapeutic candidate for obesity due to its regulatory effects on appetite and energy metabolism. Oxytocin modulates activity in brain regions

involved in reward, cognitive control, and energy homeostasis, and has been shown to reduce food intake, particularly of highly palatable foods. Animal studies have demonstrated oxytocin's potential to induce lipolysis, increase energy expenditure, and preserve lean mass during weight loss. In a pilot clinical trial, 8-week intranasal oxytocin administration (24 IU, 4 times daily) in adults with obesity resulted in a significant BMI reduction compared to placebo [39, 40, 41, 42, 43]. While these results are encouraging, further large-scale studies are needed to confirm efficacy and assess long-term safety. The fixed-dose combination therapy of phentermine and controlled-release topiramate (PHEN/TPM CR, Qsymia™) merges an appetite suppressant with a neurotherapeutic agent. Phase 3 clinical trials have shown it to be an effective long-term treatment for obesity, leading to its FDA approval in 2012 for adults with a BMI ≥ 30 kg/m² or ≥ 27 kg/m² with weight-related comorbidities [44, 45, 46, 47, 48]. In the study conducted by Hong et al., the efficacy and safety of PHEN/TPM CR were evaluated against placebo as an adjunct to standard lifestyle recommendations over a 56-week period in Korean adults with a BMI of ≥ 25 kg/m². The study showed that Korean adults with obesity experienced significant weight loss with PHEN/TPM CR compared to placebo, alongside lifestyle changes. Over 65% achieved at least a 5% reduction in body weight, along with decreases in visceral fat and improved glucose metabolism [44].

4. The Role of Physical Activity in the Treatment of Obesity

Apart from pharmacotherapy, physical activity is a key factor in treating obesity. The majority of the studies cited in our research demonstrate that in most of the analyzed articles, physical exercise was employed as a complementary strategy designed to support and potentiate the outcomes of pharmacotherapy in the management of obesity [6, 10, 11, 14, 15, 22, 36, 49]. A representative example is the study by Aronne et al., all individuals enrolled in the study received tirzepatide treatment combined with a lifestyle intervention, including a minimum of 150 minutes of weekly physical activity and maintaining a healthy diet [22]. The role of physical activity in the treatment of obesity was confirmed by a placebo-controlled, randomized trial investigating various strategies for maintaining weight loss. The study compared exercise alone (moderate-to-vigorous), liraglutide therapy alone (3.0 mg/day), a combination of both, and placebo. All active groups outperformed the placebo group and the combined exercise and liraglutide group achieved the most significant weight loss maintenance [50]. A different study examined the use of orlistat (120

mg three times daily with meals) and aerobic exercise to see how it affects body composition and aerobic capacity in obese patients. 28 obese participants were randomly allocated to a 12-week intervention involving either a hypocaloric diet with orlistat, or the same diet and orlistat combined with aerobic training. Each patient performed an exercise test every 4 weeks to assess aerobic capacity. The group assigned to exercise performed continuous training sessions (around 45 minutes each) at their anaerobic threshold intensity, three times a week. Although orlistat therapy led to enhancements in body composition and aerobic capacity by the end of the 12-week intervention, adding exercise to the treatment accelerated these improvements, achieving results within just 4 weeks [51]. Bagherzadeh-Rahmani et al. also conducted a study on tirzepatide. They demonstrated that combined resistance and aerobic exercises over six weeks outperformed tirzepatide in enhancing fitness, insulin control and muscular strength, with no added benefit from using tirzepatide alongside exercise, regardless of dose [52].

5. Discussion

Obesity as a complex metabolic disorder of multifactorial etiology involves intricate interactions between genetic, environmental, and behavioral factors. In recent years, the role of pharmacological treatment as an adjunct to non-pharmacological approaches—such as lifestyle modification, diet, and physical activity—has significantly increased. Numerous studies confirm that pharmacotherapy combined with non-pharmacological methods yields significantly better outcomes in terms of both weight loss and improvement in metabolic parameters than any single intervention used alone.

Anti-obesity medications, which act by influencing central mechanisms regulating appetite and satiety, as well as by delaying gastric emptying, have demonstrated proven efficacy in reducing body weight. This, in turn, translates into a direct reduction in the risk of cardiovascular and metabolic complications.

However, the synergistic effect of combining these therapeutic approaches is particularly important. Physical activity additionally improves insulin sensitivity, reduces inflammation, and helps preserve lean body mass. When performed regularly, it may also enhance the effects of pharmacotherapy by modulating neurohormonal mechanisms related to hunger and satiety.

Therefore, pharmacological treatment should not be considered a substitute for physical activity, but rather a complementary strategy.

Effective and, above all, sustained reduction of excessive body weight requires an individualized and integrated therapeutic approach that includes pharmacological treatment, physical activity, health education, lifestyle and dietary modifications, as well as psychological support.

Limitations to the use of pharmacotherapy in the treatment of obesity may include cost and individual tolerance to specific medications. Therefore, treatment plans should always be personalized to suit the specific needs and capabilities of each patient [2, 3, 4].

6. Conclusions

The most effective form of obesity treatment is an integrated therapeutic approach that combines pharmacotherapy with regular physical activity. Anti-obesity medications have well-documented efficacy in reducing body weight, particularly when used in conjunction with physical activity, which additionally exerts beneficial effects on glucose metabolism, lipid profile, and mental health—most importantly, it increases the likelihood of maintaining therapeutic outcomes. Further research is needed to optimize existing treatment regimens and to evaluate their long-term effects.

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